

RESEARCH ON THEORETICAL ISSUES OF REAL ESTATE MANAGEMENT

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***Abstract.** In the article, real estate management methods are theoretically studied from the point of view of functional purpose.*

Introduction

Real estate management is a management activity at the stages of the building's life cycle, covering such processes as design, construction, demolition and demolition of the facility, consulting on technical conditions for design, selection of engineering systems, development of a technical system, and operation of the facility.

Asset management is an activity to manage the financial flows of the owner of real estate.

Today, the field of professional real estate management, which in foreign practice is called surveying, is developing in the Republic of Uzbekistan. High efficiency of real estate management can only be achieved with a professional approach to it.

Surveying is an integrated approach aimed at managing facilities in a way that meets the interests of the owner of the property, its users and society as a whole.

Surveying implies consistency in the management and development of real estate. This approach places high demands on planning at all levels:

1. General; 2. Strategic; 3. Operational.

At the same time, a number of measures are being carried out (mainly feasibility studies), which allow for regular monitoring of the efficiency of the facility and, accordingly, finding ways to improve it. Management of real estate objects in accordance with an integrated approach is aimed at meeting the needs of the state to the maximum extent.

Currently, the most common types of surveying are facility management and property management, within which it is necessary to distinguish management by a specialized organization (management company), lease, trust management, concession management.

It should be noted that there are practically no legislative restrictions on the use of these management methods in any of the real estate sectors, however, over the past decade, there has been a gradual differentiation of individual approaches to managing real estate objects depending on the functional purpose of real estate (Table 1).

Let us consider the methods of managing real estate objects in more detail.

Management of a real estate object by a specialized company is often used in the residential real estate sector and is one of the three management methods provided for by the Housing Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan:

1. Management of the owners of buildings; 2. Management of a real estate object by a specialized organization (management company); 3. Management of a homeowners' association or consumer cooperative.

Table 1

Methods of real estate management from the point of view of functional purpose

Management method	Main functions according to the functional purpose of the property			
	Residential	Commercial buildings	Industrial buildings and structures	Socio-cultural facilities
Lease	Use of property in accordance with the contract; storage of property*; provision of services**; monitoring the safekeeping of entrusted property; timely payment of fees for the use of property, etc.			
Trust management	Generating income and increasing property value; maintaining property*; maintaining technical documentation; concluding contracts with repair and utility service providers; monitoring the quality of public services; searching for and attracting tenants; formulating rental policy; interacting with tenants; monitoring the safekeeping of entrusted property, etc.			
Privilege			Creation of an object; use of property in accordance with the contract; storage of property*; current and capital repairs**; modernization of the object**; control over the safety of the property of the entrusted person; timely payment of payment for the use of property, etc.	
Specialized organization management (management company)	Property management*; maintenance of technical documentation; conclusion of contracts with repair and utility service providers; quality control of public services.			
	registration, accounting and certification; information services to districts; payment management and debt collection, etc.	search and attraction of tenants; formation of rental policy; interaction-my tenant; optimization of economic data object; representing the interests of the property owner in inspections and state supervisory bodies, etc.	optimization of the economic data object; acting in the interests of the owner of the object, responding to state administration bodies; system protection of the territory, etc.	
<p>Note:</p> <p>* technical inspections and bypasses; seasonal preparation for use; current and major repairs;</p>				

A real estate management organization is a legal entity established to manage property, performs economic and operational functions related to sanitary engineering and provides maintenance services for apartment buildings.

The management organization provides intermediary services in the supply of resources such as electricity and water supply, carries out maintenance and repair work on the premises. It appears before resource supply organizations on behalf of all homeowners of the subordinate building as a single customer and as a single executor of communal services.

It should be noted that management organizations can have different specializations - only servicing or only management, as well as perform both of these functions.

The most common method of managing real estate of any functional purpose, both abroad and in Uzbekistan, is leasing. On the one hand, leasing real estate is one of the types of entrepreneurial activity, and on the other hand, it is an effective way to obtain the necessary buildings, structures, non-residential or residential premises for an appropriate fee. This indicates the dual economic nature of differential rent.

The right to lease real estate objects belongs to the owners and persons established by law. The landlord (the owner of the object or a person authorized by law or the owner) undertakes to lease the real estate object to the tenant for temporary possession and use or only for temporary use. Conclusions

According to the results of real estate management studies, when it comes to buildings that have been historically used by different organizations for different purposes, there is no alternative to trust management:

- First, only with trust management is the object principle of financing implemented: maintenance and operating costs are financed from its own income and subsidies from the budget are not required. The manager himself, as a rule, invests in the development of the object, but never requires a share of the property;

- secondly, the owner appears in the building;

- thirdly, only professional management allows the object to be developed; not randomly, but in accordance with a clear and long-term concept.

Nevertheless, trust management of real estate objects as a form of entrepreneurial activity in the Republic of Uzbekistan has not yet become widespread.

Concession is a form of public-private partnership involving the private sector on mutually beneficial terms in the effective management of state property or in the provision of services usually provided by the state.

Under a concession agreement, one party (concessionaire) undertakes to create and (or) reconstruct the property (real estate or real estate and movable property, technologically interconnected and intended for the implementation of the envisaged activities) specified in this agreement at its own expense.

The property rights that belong or belong to the other party (concession grantor) for the implementation of activities using (using) the object of the concession agreement, and the concessionaire is obliged to transfer the right of ownership and use of the object of the concession agreement to the concession holder for the period specified in this agreement.

Concession is often used in the management of state and municipal real estate, which requires large financial investments in measures to reconstruct and restore its technical and operational properties.

Thus, real estate as an economic category occupies an important place in economic theory. First of all, the land and real estate located on it are the wealth of the entire country and play a huge role in the life of society.

Secondly, real estate is an element of the process of reproduction that affects the stability of the economy and its growth.

Thirdly, real estate is one of the important indicators of the standard of living of the population, economic security and state stability. Consequently, real estate is an important element of economic relations.

Real estate objects need constant management to maintain them in a normal functional state. At the current stage of development of science in the field of real estate management, the main methods of real estate management are legal, economic, organizational and technical. The main methods of real estate management are lease, trust management, concession and management by a specialized organization. In this case, the choice of control method directly depends on the functional purpose of such an object.

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